

Micellar Composite Solution for Mediated Electrochemical Reduction of PCE: An Electrochemical Investigation

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Abstract: A micellar composite solution of cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) was utilized to stabilize and solubilized the both $[\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3]^{2+/1+}$ and perchloroethylene (PCE) in aqueous solution towards mediated electrocatalytic reduction of PCE. Initial CV studies evidences that the $[\text{Co(I)(phen)}_3]^{1+}$ was stabilized effectively in CTAB micellar solution from its decomposition. Also, the solubilization of PCE in CTAB micellar solution occurrence was reflected clearly by its mediated catalytic reduction in micellar stabilized $[\text{Co(I)(phen)}_3]^{1+}$ aqueous solution. The homogeneous rate constant (k_{homo}) between micellar solubilized $[\text{Co(I)(phen)}_3]^{1+}$ and PCE were determined by using CV studies and it found $0.89038 \times 10^1 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. Finally, GC analysis confirms the PCE reduction in micellar composite solution.

1 Introduction

Composite solutions are growing domain in various applications like selectivity, stability, and solubilization etc..Also, the increasing interest in “green chemistry” has encouraged chemists to use water as a solvent instead of organic media [1]. Interdisciplinary view of the both fields ended up in micellar solutions. It has been established that micelles can cause an acceleration or inhibition of a given reaction relative to the equivalent reaction in aqueous media [2-6]. Various transition metals such as copper, platinum, nickel, iron, rhodium, etc., have been used with caps as either catalytic centers or metalloenzyme mimics. Surprisingly, cobalt has not received as much attention as those metals. Yet, cobalt and especially simple cobalt salts of the type CoX_2 ($\text{X} = \text{Br}, \text{Cl}$) can be used as catalysts in various chemical and electrochemical synthesis of carbon-carbon coupling reactions from aromatic

halides and/or arylzinc compounds [7-9]. Mechanistic investigations demonstrated that most of these syntheses involve a reactive cobalt(I) species which is generated in situ either by electrochemical or chemical reduction of the initial cobalt(II) salt [10,11]. More importantly, it was shown that the success of these cobalt catalyzed reactions relies on the stability/reactivity duality of Co(I) that depends itself on reaction conditions. In the absence of adequate ligand, the cobalt(I) transient species undergoes a very fast disproportionation reaction leading to the loss of the catalyst via the production of inactive cobalt(0). On the other hand, the use of bipyridine or salen as ligands leads to a stable cobalt(I) species that is unable to efficiently solubilized due to low solubility of cobalt(I). Here comes surfactant, micelles can solubilize the low oxidation state of metal ions. Technetium(III) and rhenium(III) complexes have been stabilized in aqueous surfactants sodiumdodecyl sulfate (SDS), cetrytrimethylammonium bromide(CTAB), and TritonX-100 [12].

In this work, PCE was taken as model VOC because of carcinogenic effect to human due to its high use of dry cleaning and persistent contaminant found in many terrestrial and groundwater Environments [13,14]. Through CV studies, CTAB surfactant’s concentration were optimized towards stability of $[\text{Co(I)(phen)}_3]^{1+}$ in 0.1M Na_2SO_4 medium. Mediated catalysis of PCE in micellar solubilized $[\text{Co(I)(phen)}_3]^{1+}$ conducted and confirmed using CV and GC results. Solution phase electron transfer rate constant was derived for this composite solution.

2 Experiments

All chemicals CTAB, Na₂SO₄, CoCl₂·7H₂O, 2,2'-bipyridine, and NaClO₄ used were of fine grade. Tris-cobalt(II)-bipyridine perchlorate complex was prepared following the literature procedure [15] and its formation was confirmed by UV-visible spectroscopy. Cyclic voltammetric experiments were carried out using a BASi Epsilon-EC, Bioanalytical Inc., USA. A Pt wire and an Ag/AgCl were used as counter and reference electrodes, respectively. GCE was used as a working electrode: 0.198 cm² geometric area electrode for CV studies and 1.2 cm² area massive electrode for bulk electrolysis. GC electrode surface was pretreated by metallographic polishing with alumina on a velvet cloth, followed by ultrasonic cleaning in double-distilled water and washing with methanol. Solutions were made using double-distilled water. The temperature was maintained at 23 ± 0.2 °C in all experiments.

A Shimadzu model (GCMS-QP2010) was used for gas chromatography/mass spectrometry experiments. It consisted of a ZB 5 ms capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm). Helium as carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and an oven programmed between 25 and 200°C at a rate of 10°C/min were used.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Stability and solubilization by CTAB composite solution

Fig.1 explains the composite solution effect on cyclic voltammetric reduction of [Co(II)(phen)₃]^{2+/1+} complex in presence of different concentration of CTAB in 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ solution at a scan rate of 10 mVs⁻¹. At zero and low concentrations (0-0.048mM) of CTAB, there appears one cathodic reduction peak with diffusion tail around -1028 mV and a sharp anodic peak, like surface bound species behavior, around -985 mV during reverse scan. Similar CV response of [Co(II)(phen)₃]^{2+/1+} reduction continues up to the concentration of 22mM of CTAB (Fig.1 curves(a-d)) in 0.1M Na₂SO₄ solution. The surface bound species like CV response on reverse scan may be due to the preceding chemical reaction controlled electron transfer phenomena, i.e., chemical decomposition [16,17]. This preceding chemical complication is minimized completely at high concentration of CTAB (48mM) and become reasonably reversible

Fig.1. CV response' effect on various concentration of CTAB (mentioned in the figure) in 0.1M Na₂SO₄ containing 1mM [Co(II)(phen)₃]^{2+/1+} solution at GCE. Scan rate = 10mVs

electron transfer CV behavior with diffusion tail of both forward and reverse scans, as shown in Fig.1(curve e). Further, the $\Delta E_p = 88$ mV at ($E_{pc} = -1028$ mV, $E_{pa} = -940$ mV) 10mVs⁻¹ remain almost invariant within the experimental error with scan rate range 10-150 mVs⁻¹ and i_{pc} varies linearly with $v^{1/2}$ (not shown) evidences the diffusion controlled electron transfer behavior of [Co(II)(phen)₃]^{2+/1+} at 48 mM CTAB. In other words, one can say that the [Co(II)(phen)₃]^{2+/1+} complex is stabilized from decomposition, preceding chemical reaction, by solubilization of CTAB micelles at high concentrations. It is well documented that critical micellar concentration (cmc) of CTAB by CV using electrochemical probe was reported 0.6mM [18]. See that the reported work used high oxidation state(Co(III)/Co(II)) redox couple to elucidate, which is highly reversible in nature. Here, the present study involved in Co(II)/Co(I) redox couple,

which is very complicated due to its decomposition nature, as we seen above. It is to be believed that to stabilize the reduce form of $[\text{Co(I)(phen)}_3]^{1+}$ complex, 48mM of CTAB might have been needed and can be called critical micellar concentration (cmc) of CTAB in the present system. Further works will be needed to confirm the above, which are in plan to execute.

3.2 Mediated catalytic reduction in CTAB composite solution.

Though the perchloroethylene is slightly soluble in aqueous solution, PCE is not directly reduced on activated GCE in 0.1M Na_2SO_4 solution, but in 50 mM CTAB containing 0.1M Na_2SO_4 solution shows slight increase in cathodic eduction going cycle, as shown in Fig2a(curve c). This slightly increased charging current like CV response evidenced the solubility of PCE in CTAB micellar solution. Further, $\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3^{2+/1+}$ is not able to electrocatalytically reduce PCE when the absence of surfactant (not shown). Composite solution containing both 50mM of CTAB and 1mM $[\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3]^{2+/1+}$, in which micellar stabilized by solubilization of $[\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3]^{2+/1+}$, in 0.1M Na_2SO_4 solution, PCE reduction is occurred with many fold while the anodic peak eventually disappears, as shown in fig.2b(curve b). This is a similar case of mediated electrocatalytic reduction of target substrate [19,20], PCE in the present study. Because of chemical reaction between reduced mediator $[\text{Co(I)(phen)}_3]^{1+}$ and PCE, $\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3^{2+}$ is formed more and more, which enhances cathodic peak current and reason for reduced anodic peak current at the same time. At the same time, solubilization of PCE and stabilization-cum-solubilization of $[\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3]^{2+/1+}$ in micellar hydrophobic region believed to pave the way to react both the reactants effectively.

The composite solution's homogeneity and rate controlling step have further proved by a simple current function plot. The current function ($i_{\text{CAT}}/v^{1/2} c_{\text{Co(II)}}$) in presence of PCE decreases with $\log(v)$ approaching the value obtained for the micellar solubilized mediator reduction in absence of target PCE(Fig.3a curve b), typical of mediation reaction with homogenous chemical reaction as the slowest step [21]. The second order rate constant for

homogeneous electron transfer reactions are measured by the CV technique according to the method suggested by Saveant and Vianello [21] for catalytic current under pseudo first order conditions

Fig.2. (a) CV response on GCE at a scan rate of 10mVs^{-1} (conditions given in figure), (b) CV response of micelle (50mM CTAB) solubilized 1mM $[\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3]^{2+/1+}$ at GCE in 0.1M Na_2SO_4 containing two different solutions (mentioned in the figure). Scan rate = 10mVs^{-1} .

(excess of target substrate. The cathodic peak current in absence (i_{pc}) and presence (i_{CAT}) were calculated from CV of micellar solubilized mediator alone and presence of 30mM of PCE, respectively. Here, the mediator to target substrate ratio is 1:30, which obeys the pseudo first order conditions. The second order rate constant (k_{homo}) for the

homogeneous reaction is calculated using the following equation:

$$i_{\text{CAT}}/i_{\text{pc}} = (1/0.447)(RT/nF)^{1/2} (\sigma k_{\text{homo}} c_z/v)^{1/2} \quad \text{---(1)}$$

where c_z is the concentration of the target substrate (PCE here), v (Vs^{-1}), k_{homo} ($\text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) and σ the stoichiometric coefficient and other parameters has usual meanings. If n and σ are known prior, k_{homo} can be calculated from the slope of the plot $i_{\text{CAT}}/i_{\text{pc}}$ versus $v^{-1/2}$, according to the equation (1). The obtained plot (Fig.3b) is reasonably linear ($R^2 = 0.9625$) with a slope (57.8167 (mVs^{-1}) $^{1/2}$) at studied scan rates.

Fig.3. (a) The change of current function with $\log(v)$, (b) Effect of catalytic current with $v^{-1/2}$. The data obtained from the CV response of 30mM PCE in (50mM CTAB+1mM $[\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3]^{2+/1+}$ +0.1M Na_2SO_4) aqueous solution.

Using the slope value 57.8167 (mVs^{-1}) $^{1/2}$, k_{homo} is calculated with the help of eqn.(1) with $n = 1$ and the σ as 4 because 4 mole of Co(II) complex is needed

to reduce 1 mole of PCE. The found k_{homo} is $0.8904 \times 10^1 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. In order to confirm the composite solution's effect of mediated catalysis, bulk electrolysis were carried out for 20mM PCE in presence of 50mM CTAB in 0.1M Na_2SO_4 aqueous solution. A big carbon electrode (1.2 cm^2) as cathode, Pt and Ag/AgCl as counter and reference electrode, respectively were used to carry out constant potential electrolysis, at the potential of -1250mV in one hour duration. The ether extracted samples from bulk electrolysis were analysed with GC, which is depicted in Fig.4. There appears a reduced (80% reduction in peak area) PCE peak at retention time of 8.8 min in electrolyzed sample (Fig.4 curve b), Where appears at before electrolysis (Fig.4 curve a) evidences the effectiveness of micellar composite solution on mediated reduction of PCE at given experimental conditions.

Fig.4. GC of PCE(20mM) in different conditions: (a) Before electrolysis; (b) after electrolysis. Working solution: 0.1M Na_2SO_4 + 50mM CTAB + 1mM $[\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3]^{2+/1+}$

Conclusions: In this study, CTAB micellar composite solution was successfully utilized to stabilize and solubilized the both $[\text{Co(I)(phen)}_3]^{1+}$ and PCE. Reversibility of $[\text{Co(II)(phen)}_3]^{2+/1+}$ CV studies evidence the CTAB micellar composites

formation. Mediated catalytic reduction of PCE in micellar stabilized $[\text{Co}(\text{I})(\text{phen})_3]^{1+}$ aqueous solution confirms the solubilization of PCE in CTAB micellar solution. Also, CV of micellar solubilized $[\text{Co}(\text{I})(\text{phen})_3]^{1+}$ and PCE were used to calculate their homogeneous rate constant ($k_{\text{homo}} = 0.89038 \times 10^1 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$). Micellar composite solution effectively reduces the PCE, which is confirmed by GC analysis. Further work is in progress to understand the in-depth of composite solution effect and its utility of VOCs degradation.

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